

INSTAR signs landmark MoU with TTA

Clear measures to strengthen the EU-South Korea Digital Partnership

On Thursday 5 September 2024, INSTAR signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with TTA (Telecommunications Technology Association) hosted by the Ayuntamiento de Madrid.

The event was attended by Tanya Suarez, INSTAR coordinator from BluSpecs, and Damir Filipovic, INSTAR ITFs activities leader from and AIOTI, and Antonio Kung from Trialog on behalf of INSTAR, along with Mr. Seung-hyun Son, President of TTA of the Republic of Korea.

This MoU, the first INSTAR has signed with an international partner (South Korea) within the scope of the project, aims to align European and South Korean priorities in emerging technologies standardisation.

The INSTAR-ROK International Task Force (ITF)

With both regions playing key roles in technological innovation, this MoU is set to become a critical step toward global alignment on standardisation priorities, making this partnership timely and essential.

By the end of this year, the collaboration will establish a joint International Task Force (ITF).

This initiative aims to achieve several goals:

- Identify standardisation priorities on both sides across the six technology areas covered by INSTAR (5G/6G, Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity/Digital ID, Data Technologies, Internet of Things, and Quantum Technologies).
- Agree on common European and South Korean standardisation priorities.
- Develop a joint standardisation roadmap for these priorities to be promoted to international Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) to become work items.

This collaboration will ensure that the priorities identified by the INSTAR European Task Forces are visible within international standardisation organisations.

Damir Filipovic, INSTAR ITFs activities leader.

After the first year of collaboration, a review will be conducted to assess the results and agree on the next set of common priorities.

INSTAR ITFs role within the EU Digital Partnerships

The impact of this MoU is significant, as it directly supports the [EU-ROK Digital Partnership](#).

This MoU will strengthen the EU-ROK Digital Partnership by supporting its implementation in key areas of standardisation, including 5G/6G, AI, and cybersecurity. It aims to deliver tangible outcomes in international standardisation bodies through work items proposed or supported by both European and South Korean representatives.

Tanya Suarez, INSTAR coordinator from BluSpecs.

By promoting European standardisation priorities, this collaboration strengthens and reinforces the partnership between the EU and South Korea, positioning both regions as global leaders in technological standardisation and regulatory alignment.

The INSTAR-TTA collaboration gives all stakeholders on both sides the opportunity to shape the EU-ROK standardisation priorities and ensure that they are acknowledged by international SDOs.

Our consortium

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To stay updated on the latest developments and milestones from INSTAR and its collaboration with TTA, we invite you to [subscribe to our newsletter](#).

By signing up, you will be the first to receive news on key updates, and exclusive insights into how this partnership is shaping the future of global standardisation!

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